

LITERASI MEDIA INTERNET DI KALANGAN MAHASISWA
UPN “VETERAN” JAWA TIMUR

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ABSTRAK

Internet dengan perkembangan teknologi komunikasi yang semakin lama semakin meningkat, mendekatkan dan semakin memanjakan usernya dengan berbagai informasi. Banyak ragamnya informasi di internet bisa menjadi manfaat juga bisa menjadi masalah. Internet bisa dikatakan susah sekali untuk dihindari, terlebih-lebih saat ini blank spot area semakin menipis. Penelitian ini menggambarkan bagaimana penggunaan internet dikalangan mahasiswa sehubungan dengan literasi media internet hingga pada pemahaman apakah mahasiswa bersikap kritis dengan konten media yang digunakan atau dikonsumsi. Kampus UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur sebagai Kampus Bela Negara tentunya dalam implementasinya adalah dengan mengenali AGHT informasi yang tidak mungkin terhindari lagi. Mahasiswa UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur sebagai warga Surabaya yang baru-baru ini dicanangkan sebagai Cyber City tentu harus berbenah dalam hal ini. Cyber City membawa konsekuensi semakin lengkapnya jaringan internet di kota ini. Pengambilan data melalui observasi partisipatori, *indepth interview*, *focus group discussion* dan studi pustaka untuk menggali lebih mendalam bagaimana penggunaan internet di kalangan mahasiswa UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur.

Kata kunci : mahasiswa, internet, media, literasi media

INTERNET MEDIA LITERACY FOR UPN “VETERAN” EAST JAVA STUDENTS

ABSTRACT

Internet with the development of communication technology is increasingly increasing, closer and increasingly pamper its users with various information. A lot of the variety of information on the internet can be a benefit too can be a problem. The Internet can be very difficult to avoid, especially when the blank spot area is running low. This study illustrates how internet usage among students in relation with internet media literacy to the understanding of whether students are critical with media content used or consumed. Campus UPN "Veteran" Jawa Timur as State Defense College course in implementation is to identify AGHT information which is not inevitable anymore. Student UPN "Veteran" East Java as Surabaya citizen who recently proclaimed as Cyber City certainly have to clean up in this case. Cyber City brings the consequences of more complete internet network in this city. Collecting data through participatory observation, in-depth interviews, focus group discussions and literature to explore more deeply how the use of the Internet among students UPN "Veteran" East Java.

Keyword : student, internet, media, media literacy

PRELIMINARY

Information grip, ease in accessing information through the internet provides many benefits to various circles of society. The rapid development of communication technology provides the consequence of ease in accessing information. Rubin (1998) explains that what is meant by media literacy is the understanding of the source, the communication technology, the code used, the resulting message, the selection, the interpretation and the impact of the message. Hobbs (1996) describes as a process of accessing, critically analyzing media messages and creating messages using media tools. Changes in communication patterns occur that in addition to consumers then the user can also juda as a manufacturer.

Indonesian Internet Service Provider Association (APJII) on November 7, 2016 released internet users survey data in Indonesia. Noted that internet users in Indonesia reached 132.7 million people from the total population of Indonesia as much as 256.2 million inhabitants. The largest portion of internet users is Java with 86.3 million users and users of 18.6 million students. (<http://techno.okezone.com/read/2016/11/07/207/1535401/apjii-rilis-survei-pengguna-internet-indonesia>) Global information flows are certainly hit students with various consequences. Undeniably can lead to both positive and negative.

Student UPN "Veteran" East Java is part of Surabaya society which recently declared as Cyber City. The ability of media literacy such as internet becomes mandatory for the students especially UPN "Veteran" East Java as New State University considering in the global information era such as the current media literacy becomes an answer so that students are not left behind and foreign in digital environment.

This study illustrates how the use of the Internet among students in relation to Internet media literacy and whether students are critical with the media content used or consumed. This research is expected to be the input of university managers in order to design the media literacy education. In addition to this, the study is also expected to be a guide for online mass media managers to be able to design and create creative messages to attract students

Based on the above description of the background then the formulation of problems to be used in this study are: How the understanding of UPN "Veteran" East Java students about media literacy, knowledge structure and skills of their internet media literacy and implementation in the lecture?

Previous Research

Previous research conducted by Fantin (2010) describes the culture of culture that poses different challenges from educators. Digital culture requires mastery of different codes from different languages, away from literacy skills. This provides an overview to re-understand the concept of literacy, media, digital and information.

Other research is also done by Rahmi (2013) that the mass media that give life change society. Competition is very tight making mass media scramble viewers so that profit becomes the number one when compared with educational content content.

Media Literacy

Silverblatt (2007) that media literacy understanding is traditionally defined as an ability to access, analyze, and create. Ferrington (2006) describes the understanding of media literacy in the expanded seventies including the ability to read film, television and visual media texts because the study of media education began by following the development of the media area. Hobbs (1996) explains that media literacy is the process of accessing, critically analyzing media messages and creating messages using media tools. Brown (1998) media literacy is the ability to analyze and appreciate literary works, and to communicate effectively through good writing. Rubin (1998) explains that media literacy is the understanding of sources, communication technologies, codes used, messages produced, selection, interpretation and impact of the message.

The two most common components of media literacy definition are the awareness of many media messages and critical ability to analyze and question what is seen, read and watched (Hobbs, 2001; Silverblatt, 1995; Singer & Singer, 1998). Five concepts of media literacy under the Center of Media Literacy (Kellner & Sahre, 2005) are as follows: all media messages are "constructed"; media messages are constructed in a creative language according to their rules; individuals interpret the message depending on their understanding of the message they are capturing from the media; media has a point of view and contains its own value; almost all media messages have a vested interest or power.

Internet as Medium Mass Media

The Internet as a transitional media is the answer to the weaknesses as well as the lack of print and electronic mass media. Delayed Feedback which was originally a weakness over the internet was changed to Immediate Feedback. The news yesterday is read now turns into news now read now, yesterday's news is the archive for our reading whenever we need. The reliability of the internet in presenting information is an attraction for various mass media to migrate to make use of it. Many print media that make the website address on the internet to become online media, as well as radio and television using the streaming path. Not only that, the development of the current trend is on the online social media was much used as a media sharing.

Internet that was originally developed militarily developed to be utilized by the general public. Internet that originally only as a tool, is now developed as a medium that has the ability interactivity.

Student as Media Audience

Students are part of the adolescent who is often described as a stage of childhood development into adulthood characterized by general physical changes as well as cognitive and social development. It is believed that the development of adolescence is directly proportional to adult life. Through the media, students learn to recognize the outside life as well as get the socialization of sovereign values in the community according to reality that is portrayed by the media.

Dealing with the media, teenagers show a dynamic character considering basically always curious, easily affected and tend to receive just the media content (The Habibie Center, 2010: 7) On the other hand teenagers familiar with technology, not afraid of new things and tend to idealist (Zimic, 2009)

New Media Developments

Everett M. Rogers in his book Communication Technology; The New Media in Society (in Mulyana, 1999) says that in communications relations in the community, it is known 4 (four) communications era namely the era of writing, the era of print media, the era of telecommunication media and the era of interactive communication media. In the last era of

known interactive media communication media of computer, videotext and teletext, teleconferencing, cable TV and so on. (Mulyana, 2004) The era of interactive communication is also called the new media era. New media words appeared to reveal the rapid development of media and world media communications in the late 1980s. The media in question is always at the level of technological change, institutions and culture never stops. Here are the social, economic and cultural changes in which new media are associated (Lister, 2009):

- a. The change from modernity to postmodernity. Striving to characterize the depth and social change of society and the economy forward, is correlated with cultural change. In aesthetic and economic terms, the new media is usually seen as a marker of that kind of change.
- b. Intensify globalization process. Combining the State and its boundaries in the level of trade, organization, customs and culture, identity and beliefs in which new media are seen as contributing elements.
- c. A substitute in the Western world, the industrial era and post-industrial information age. An employee turnover, expertise, investment and profits in the production of materials for services and industry information where the use of new media is seen promises

New Media is used to point to the following :

- a. New textual experiences: new genres and text forms, entertainment and consumption patterns of the media (computer games, simulations, special effects cinema)
- b. New ways to represent the world: a medium that can not always be clearly defined, offering new representational possibilities and experiences (virtual environments, interactif multimedia)
- c. New relationships between subjects (users and consumers) with media technology: changes in the use and acceptance of images and communication media in everyday life and in meaning placed in media technology.
- d. New experiences in relation to personification, identity and community: changes in social and personal experience in time, space and place (on a global and local scale) that have implications for the way humans experience themselves and the place of humanity in the world.
- e. A new conception of biological body relationships with media technology: the challenge of accepting the distinction between human and non-nature, and technology, body (and media) instead of technology, original and virtual.

All forms of new media have been proven to facilitate many people, especially in the field of communication and information. But not many know the characteristics of new media that today almost everyone uses it.

Here are the new media traits by Dennis McQuail (2011):

1. Interconnectivity
2. Individual as well as the recipient or sender of the message
3. Be interactive
4. Diverse usage as an open character
5. Its nature is everywhere

RESEARCH METHODS

The method to be used in this research is explorative qualitative research method. This method is used to get the breadth and depth of data and to get how the use of the Internet among students UPN "Veteran" Java East. Exploration will be conducted to explore how the mahasis is critical with the media content used or consumed.

Data collection techniques that will be used is by using indepth interview and Focus Group Discussion on some UPN "Veteran" East Java students. This technic was chosen because it allows researchers to get the perception of respondents based on the point of view of respondents themselves and able to capture the experience of respondents with various background back. Respondents were selected using nonprobability sampling / purposive sampling method. Respondent is a student of UPN "Veteran" East Java. The number of respondents is not predetermined. However, data collection will be discontinued if the information obtained is considered sufficient.

The data will be analyzed qualitatively, Taylor in Pujileksono (2014) states that qualitative data analysis techniques is a process in detailing, finding themes and formulating hypotheses (ideas). While Bogdan and Biklen in Moleong (2007) state that data analysis is an effort done by organizing data, sorting, synthesizing, searching and finding patterns, finding what is important and learned, and deciding what is told to others. Therefore, in this study, the collected data will then be organized, sorted, coded and categorized based on the answers that appear for later in maknai and concluded. As described in the table below.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Target Audience

Gender	: Male and Female
Age	: 18 – 24 Years
Status	: UPN “Veteran” Jawa Timur Student
Education	: S1 Study

The results of this study illustrates that students prefer to use smartphones in accessing the internet. They assume that smartphones provide many more meaningful facilities in supporting them surf the internet. The applications contained on the smartphone is very helpful their internet activity. All the time students use the internet to socialize. Many of their friends earn from the introduction in cyberspace or cyber. In addition to smartphone students also use laptops in accessing the internet considering the laptop is more reliable in exploring the online world especially when associated with online games or images editing.

Students access the internet almost every time, some menggunakan that wake up directly held is smartphonenya device to access the internet both Instagram and other social media also read the WA messages that are not read while sleeping.

Social media are popular and contemporary according to them on Instagram, online social media such as facebook, twitter, path, tumblr more as a complement in beronline social media. Students tend to get the latest news or information through online social media. In online social media where information becomes viral then they find out on the general sites.

In certain college students interested in the world of politics but not far away with what they are hobby. Students feel uneasy with information that is confusing on the internet, especially political issues. Students do not want to directly jump in the online squabbles that occur in online social media.

National Development University "Veteran" East Java has a website and links page that relates to students and studies. More students get into the Siamik because it is directly related to their needs. Through the ceramics they can get a list of names and npm of their friends who are at any time needed for group work.

UPN "veteran" East Java also has e-learning, students only use it at the time of task only. Students in some opinions actually want to rely on the existing material in E-learning but inadequate

UPN "Veteran" East Java lack of facilitation in students to surf, lack of electric plugs, wifi that often disconnected and even can not connect at all and their supporting facilities to surf that feel less support by the institution.

Conclusion

Students as informants provide information that they access the internet to bersosialita. They need the internet to learn only on the needy moment. Critical attitude is not visible to students, they seem to receive information just like that. Indifferent cultures in the environment also impact on the cyber environment they are in every day. It needs a Sociotechnical approach in the face of this case.

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